
The Effectiveness of Cooperative Learning Method Type Talking Stick in Improving Students' Vocabulary Memorization

Syamsia & Nurfaiza Rusdy*

* English Department, STKIP Kie Raha Ternate
Correspondence: syamsia@stkipkieraha.ac.id

Abstract

The aim of this research is to know the effectiveness of students in memorizing English vocabulary through cooperative learning model using talking stick. Vocabulary is important to be master since someone can't talk without knowing vocabulary. At some junior schools the students have a low mastery of vocabulary. This research uses the Classroom Action Research; this research was conducted at Mts Al-Khautsar Kao. The subjects of this research were students of class VIII, totaling 27 students consisting of 14 girls and 13 boys. The research has some techniques and some instruments to gain both qualitative and quantitative data. The techniques are observation, interview, testing, and documenting study. To analyze the data, the researcher started by doing reflection of the cycles of the study. This means that the data were analyzed continually since the implementation of the action began. As this research was a classroom action research, therefore, to avoid subjectivity, the researcher involved the research members to find their perceptions, opinions and suggestions in analyzing the data. The result of the reflection in cycle I was not improved so this research continues in cycle II. Based on the students' result in cycle II, it was found out that the students' vocabulary score was improved. It indicated that the use of talking stick technique could encourage and motivate them to retain and enrich their vocabulary.

Keywords: *cooperative learning, talking stick, vocabulary memorization*

© Langua – 2021

1. Background

This research is about the effectiveness of students in memorizing English vocabulary. Vocabulary mastery has significant role in achieving four language skills. Before acquiring four language skills, it is important to understand vocabulary first. Cameron (2001:72) states that building up a useful vocabulary is central to the learning a foreign language at primary level. From this view, it is clear that vocabulary mastery is vital in language acquisition. Vocabulary as the basic aspect of English supports listening, speaking, reading, and writing. It should be paid an attention in teaching learning process. Vocabulary is important to be master since someone can't talk without knowing vocabulary. At some junior schools the students have a low mastery of vocabulary. It is shown that the students

need long time to mention a name of a thing, students get a problem in pronouncing the word, and they often mention wrong words in pointing a thing. Teaching vocabulary particularly in junior high school becomes essential to improving vocabulary. Vocabulary cannot be separated from other elements in English teaching learning process in junior high school because vocabulary influences the ability of students in studying English language.

The researchers have made an observation in Mts Al-Kautsar Kao and the researchers found fact that the students faced the difficulties in English Vocabulary. The researcher found some problems are caused by several factors. They are: based on the score of daily test in English, many students have low in mastery of vocabulary. And also based on the result of interview to the English teacher and the students, the researcher found some reason: 1) most of the students feel that English is the most difficult lesson to be learned, the students are not brave to express their idea, they afraid if they make mistake their friends will laugh to them, 2) the teacher conducts less communicative class, the teacher is not able to optimize media and never uses anything media. Like other students, students of Mts Alkhautsar Kao have difficulties in mastering vocabulary. Remembering vocabulary needs a hard work because the pronunciation and spelling are different. In order to follow the demand of English skill, the teacher tries to find out a good technique in teaching vocabulary.

Based on the problems above, the researcher would like to give a solution to solve that problem. The researcher tried to applying the talking stick type cooperative method to help students understand and enrich their knowledge of English vocabulary. The cooperative method is a learning model that focuses on the use of small groups of students to work together in maximizing learning conditions to achieve learning goals in the cooperative learning class. There are several types of cooperative learning, one of which is the talking stick model type (Suyatno, 2009: 71). The talking stick type cooperative learning model is a group learning model with the help of sticks. The talking stick learning model is very suitable to be applied to elementary, junior high and high school students. In addition to practicing speaking, this learning will create a fun atmosphere and keep students active.

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1. Vocabulary

According to Manser (in Loi, 2020:75) vocabulary is the total number of words in a language. In vocabulary terms, Lado (in Zalmansyah, 3013:264) reveals their levels of difficulty in vocabulary, namely: easy vocabulary, normal vocabulary, and special (difficult) vocabulary. Things that affect students having difficulty mastering foreign vocabulary include the effects of hearing the words, pronouncing the words, reading the words, practicing interpreting followed by expressing them. (Practice from meaning to expression), and write the words (Wring the words). It should be noted that students are taught vocabulary regularly and continuously, and use it in daily practice. If a student only learns a foreign language and practices it only in the classroom, this will not guarantee that the student is proficient and mastering a foreign language.

Vocabulary in language learning, including English, is an important thing to master. Vocabulary can be interpreted as a collection of words that someone can understand. Someone who understands vocabulary well will also have an impact on good communication processes Nunan (in Herlina, 2015:115). Another opinion states that vocabulary is a collection of words commonly used to communicate for everyone (Bamhart, 2008). Someone will be younger in understanding a language (communicating) if they first understand the meaning of the vocabulary used.

2.2. Cooperative Learning Method

A cooperative learning method is a learning approach that focuses on using small groups of students to work together in maximizing learning conditions to achieve learning goals.

According to lie (in Firdaus, 2019:94). The cooperative learning model or also known as mutual cooperation is a teaching system that provides opportunities for students to work together with fellow students in completing structured tasks. Furthermore, according to Asma and Ahmad, and Mahmood

(in Wibisono,2017:4). It has several principles, namely the learning paradigm that is centered on students, collaboration in groups to build knowledge and skill possessed, participatory learning processes, relative teaching (facilitators create strategies that are appropriate so that all students have high motivation in undergoing the learning process), and learning is fun and does not present a stressful atmosphere for student.

Cooperative learning methods arise because of developments in the existing learning system. Cooperative learning methods replace individual learning systems. Where the teacher continues to provide information (the teacher is the center) and students just listen.

2.3. Talking Stick

According to Suprijono (in Suhardiana, 2018:43) cooperative learning model talking stick type is learning that can encourage students to dare to express an opinion. According to Widodo (in Basuki,2017:35) talking stick is a learning model that uses a stick as a tool for turning instructions, students who get a stick will be asked a question and have to answer it, then relay the stick is moved into the hands of other students. And so on until all students get sticks and questions. Meanwhile, according to Kurniasih & Sani (in Dewi,2017:3) Talking stick learning model describes one of several models cooperative learning. This learning model use a support stick. The stick was used as a tool as or part of the opportunity to obtain or giving answer to questions from the teacher after students.

The talking stick type cooperative learning step begins with the teacher explain the learning objectives, the teacher forms groups, teachers prepare a stick, the teacher delivers the main material, students discuss, teacher welcomes group members to cover the contacts of the reading, the teacher gives a stick to cored one member of the group randomly then the students give to his friend who was holding the stick he answered questions from the teacher. Other students may help answer questions if members of the group cannot answer questions, as well as making conclusions and conducting evaluation or the assessment is continued by closing the lesson.

3. Research Methods

This research uses the Classroom Action Research method; classroom action research (CAR) is a type of research conducted by teachers or researchers to solve learning problems in class. Classroom action research is a cyclical study, in which the design follows the CAR design proposed by Kemmis and Taggart. There are four steps of classroom action research, namely: planning, implementing, observing and reflecting. This research was conducted at Mts Al-Khautsar Kao. The subjects of this research were students of class VIII, totaling 27 students consisting of 14 girls and 13 boys.

3.1. Data Collecting Techniques

The research has some techniques and some instruments to gain both qualitative and quantitative data. The techniques are observation, interview, testing, and documenting study.

3.2. Data Analysis

To analyze the data, the researcher started by doing reflection of the cycles of the study. This means that the data were analyzed continually since the implementation of the action began. As this research was a classroom action research, therefore, to avoid subjectivity, the researcher involved the research members to find their perceptions, opinions and suggestions in analyzing the data.

4. Research Results

Based on preliminary observations made before the learning process, it was found that the main weakness of students so that they had difficulty learning English vocabulary properly was because they were weak in memorizing vocabulary skills. This research was carried out as well as solving problems of learning English in the class which became research subject.

4.1. Initial conditions (Pre Research)

The results of the pre-cycle showed that only 8 students had completed learning while 10 students had not finished (scored <75). Learning English at MTS / SMP is usually done for 30 minutes with a lecture learning model, the use of the lecture learning method is very good, but there are still some students who still have difficulty memorizing vocabulary. At the beginning of learning English, many students were happy but in the middle of learning it became conducive because the children felt bored.

Here we can conclude from the results of the pre-cycle scores of students who have not completed 10 students and students who have passed 8 students, this shows the students' ability in English vocabulary <75 The percentage of students' English vocabulary scores is 44.4% and an average value of 69.7.

Based on the results of observations and tests of students' initial abilities, actions were taken so that the students' mastery of English vocabulary could improve. One of the actions the researcher took was using the talking stick cooperative learning model. The learning plan is arranged in such a way by utilizing the speaking stick type cooperative learning model so that students' mastery of English vocabulary can be improved.

4.2. The Result of Cycle I

Planning

In the action planning stage of the first cycle, the activities carried out are compiling a learning implementation plan (RPP) which consists of two meetings. The lesson plans that have been compiled are consulted with the class VIII English teacher so that it can be adjusted to the situation and conditions at school. The lesson plan that has been agreed upon is used as a reference for researchers in carrying out learning by using speaking tokens and compiling observation sheets for students that are used as a guide for observing students' abilities during this time so that researchers can find out students' abilities regarding the material being taught during the teaching and learning process.

Implementation and observation

During the learning process, there are two activities carried out simultaneously, namely implementation and observation which are carried out in an effort to improve students' English vocabulary mastery and observations of activities being carried out by researchers who act as teachers to students. Implementation is carried out based on the RPP that has been compiled. Cycle I consists of 2x meetings with each meeting one lesson hour (1x35).

The first meeting was held on Wednesday. Lessons began at 07.35 WIT and ended at 09.54 WIT. The material taught at this meeting is about vocabulary. In the initial activity, the researcher entered the VIII class of student. The teacher greets and greets students with the words "good morning, students?" students answer the teacher's suggestions by saying "good morning miss". The teacher asks students to prepare stationery and books. The teacher attendance students after that appreciates after the students can be in good condition. Appreciation is done by the teacher by asking students about related material to be taught "do you know what vocabulary is? Students answer questions from the teacher together, most of the students answer the teacher's questions loudly. The teacher asks again "who knows what tables, chairs, windows, floors are in English? Some students try to answer questions from the teacher, but there are still some answers from students who are still wrong, such as mentioning the table means the window. The teacher corrects students' answers which are spoken verbally. Then the teacher mentioned that today we will learn about vocabulary in English.

In the core activity, the teacher forms students in a circle then gives the context of the word and the meaning of the word about the "vocabulary" material to students. The teacher instructs all students to sing the song they like along with the song that the stick that is held by the student is given to the student exchanging relay when the song stops, the student who gets the stick will be asked a question

about an English vocabulary given until so on and all students get their turn and students answer. The teacher confirmed the students' answers.

In the closing activity, the teacher provides opportunities for students to ask questions. Teachers and students together put together the subject matter. The teacher gives closing words and words of motivation then greeting before leaving.

The second meeting was held on the same day, Wednesday at 10.00 WIT. The material taught at this meeting was to continue learning about "vocabulary" in the initial activity, the teacher and researcher entered the VIII class room. Teacher greets students and asks students to prepare books and stationery. Students are still so busy and don't pay attention to teacher instructions so that the teacher counts the numbers from one to three to attract students' attention so that students can sit quietly in their seats. The activities carried out by the teacher did not attract the attention of students because students were still not ready to receive lessons and were still busy themselves so that the teacher immediately took action by trying to divert their attention in order to go forward by asking students "who still remembers what yesterday's lesson was about?" students answer together "Regarding" vocabulary "miss" The teacher then asks again "who knows what" vocabulary "means? Students answer simultaneously, then the teacher points to one of the female students to answer the teacher's question. "The noun" miss "answered Jinan. The teacher then asks all the students "how many nouns are there?" the student answered "there are many" what? " Ask the teacher again. The student then mentions one prepay and the teacher confirms the student's answer.

The teacher repeats what the English table is, the chair, the window, the floor. When the teacher repeats the vocabulary that has been given, the teacher also repeats the word pronunciation. The vocabulary that is recited by the teacher is pronounced in English and Indonesian. This is done so that students are able to pronounce it well. The teacher then invites students to play a game that is done using the talking stick. The teacher explains how to play the game before the game is played. Students are formed in a circle or in a circle like the first meeting then one student is given a stick or wood and all students sing simultaneously as the song sticks are held running to all students when the song stops students who are still holding the stick will be asked questions about vocabulary which has been memorized earlier until all the students get their turn. Students answer vocabulary in English, vocabulary in Indonesian, and how to pronounce in English. The teacher corrects the students' memorization by asking to read the vocabulary they have memorized in front of their friends.

In the closing activity, the teacher gives students the opportunity to ask questions as usual. Students and teachers together conclude the subject matter. At the end of the lesson students are asked to make any 5 nouns and then memorize them in front of the class. The teacher closes the lesson with a greeting.

Observations are made by researchers and English teachers who act as teachers. The position of the researcher as a passive participant, so that he can observe the nets of the learning process. Observations are carried out in conjunction with the actions taken to improve students' mastery of English vocabulary. Observations are carried out during the learning process. Observations consist of two types, namely the observation of student activities during the learning process. Observation guidelines regarding things that must be observed during the learning process of teacher activities have been stated in the observation sheet for teacher activities, the observation guidelines regarding things that must be observed in the learning process of student activities are contained in student observation sheets.

Tabel.1 Result from Students' Observation Sheet

No	Name	Liveliness	Ability to Remember Vocabulary	Bravery	Memorization ability	Pronunciation Vocabulary	score
1	P1	✓		✓	✓	✓	Enough
2	P2			✓	✓	✓	Not enough
3	P3	✓		✓	✓	✓	Enough
4	P4	✓				✓	Not enough
5	P5				✓	✓	Not Enough
6	P6	✓	✓	✓	✓		Enough
7	P7	✓	✓		✓	✓	Enough
8	P8	✓	✓	✓	✓		Enough
9	P9	✓	✓	✓	✓		Enough
10	P10	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Enough
11	P11	✓	✓	✓	✓		Enough
12	P12	✓	✓	✓	✓		Enough
13	L13	✓	✓	✓	✓		Enough
14	L14	✓	✓	✓	✓		Enough
15	L15	✓	✓	✓	✓		Enough
16	L16	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Enough
17	L17	✓	✓			✓	Not enough
18	L18	✓	✓			✓	Not Enough
19	L19	✓	✓			✓	Not Enough
20	L20	✓	✓			✓	Not enough
21	L21	✓	✓			✓	Not enough
22	L22	✓	✓			✓	Not enough
23	L23	✓	✓			✓	Not enough
24	L24	✓	✓			✓	Not enough

Based on the result of the observation sheet, there are 13 students who have completed the memorization of moderate vocabulary while 11 students have not finished memorizing vocabulary.

After applying the talking stick method, the average value of student learning outcomes was 70.83, 12 of the 24 students had reached the high category, indicating that there were 14 students in the pre-cycle in general; the students had not reached the target results.

Table 2: Description of the score of cycle I

No.	Score	Absolute frequency	Relative frequency
1	very high	2	18,4
2	High	15	88.55
3	moderate	11	40,1
4	Low	1	4,3
5	Very low	0	0

Reflections

Reflection is a step to reassess the actions that have been taken during cycle I. Reflection is carried out by researchers and teachers. Researchers and teachers were discussing the actions that have been taken and reveal things that need to be improved. Improvements need to be made to improve students' English vocabulary mastery. The result of the reflection in cycle I was not improved so this research continues in cycle II.

4.3. The Result of Cycle II

Planning

Planning in cycle II is an effort to improve the results obtained in cycle I. The planning stage is carried out in cycle II, namely compiling RPP regarding holiday text which consists of one meeting. The lesson plans that have been compiled are in consultation with the English teacher to suit the conditions of students and schools. The lesson plans that were compiled underwent a slight change based on the reflections that had been done in the first cycle so that the students' mastery of English vocabulary could improve on pending texts because children were more likely to like short stories like holidays so they could increase vocabulary memorization.

Implementation

Treatment actions are carried out based on the prepared RPP. The implementation was carried out in cycle II; there was a slight change with the implementation carried out in cycle I. The treatment in cycle II was only one meeting one lesson hour (1x35 minutes). Learning will be carried out on Thursday, 20 August 2020. Learning begins at 08.00 WIT and ends at 10.00 WIT. The material taught at this meeting is about "holiday text" in the initial activity, the teacher and researcher enter the VIII class room. The teacher greets and greets students with the words "good morning students?" students answer with the words "morning miss" the teacher asks students to prepare writing instruments. The teacher presents students by distributing student worksheets that have been made for each student. In the main activity, the teacher provides holiday texts by writing them on the blackboard. The teacher writes the vacation vocabulary text on the blackboard so that students can write or answer the questions on the LKS by filling in the answers that have questions in the Essay form if the student has answered all the questions given then the students are made in a circle, all students are asked to sing as in the first cycle of learning with one student holding a stick or wood, along with the song stick is spread to all students when the song stops, the student who is still holding the stick will be asked a question containing the holiday text until all students have a turn. Students answer the questions given by reading by closing the worksheets they are working on the vocabulary they are working on the LKS then the teacher answers them properly. After everything was done, the teacher and students both pronounced the vocabulary they had just learned aloud. This is done to check students' memorization. Checking is also seen when students answer questions from teacher. In the closing activity, the teacher and students together conclude the subject matter that has been learned. The teacher gives messages to students not to be bored to memorize English vocabulary. The teacher gives a moral message to students after all students collect the questions given. The teacher closes the lesson with a greeting.

Observation

Observations in cycle II were carried out by researchers and English teachers as teachers. The position of the researcher as a passive participant, so that he can observe the nets of the learning process. The observations were carried out in conjunction with the actions taken to improve the students' English vocabulary mastery.

Table 3 The Students' result

No	Name	Score	Information
1	IN	100	Completed
2	DB	100	Completed
3	RH	80	Completed
4	FS	80	Completed
5	MA	100	Completed
6	SY	100	Completed
7	SAL	100	Completed
8	WID	80	Completed
9	NA	80	Completed
10	KA	100	Completed
11	JU	80	Completed
12	LI	100	Completed
13	NAF	100	Completed
14	UR	100	Completed
15	RIF	100	Completed
16	RAI	100	Completed
17	JIH	100	Completed
18	AIRI	100	Completed
19	HEN	80	Completed
20	AIR	60	Not finished yet
21	JAM	100	Completed
22	RAF	80	Completed
23	AJI	80	Completed
24	RAF	65	Not finished yet

Based on the table above, there are 22 students who have completed the memorization of moderate vocabulary while 2 students have not finished memorizing vocabulary.

The table above shows that the average score of students increased from 70.83 in the results of the observation sheet of the students' ability in cycle II to 93.54, so the percentage increase increased by 9.09%, so in cycle II the study was said to be successful because it had fulfilled KKM 97.

Reflection

Reflection is a step to reassess the actions that have been taken during II. Researchers and teachers together discuss the results of the reflections that teachers and researchers do show that there has been an increase in the activities undertaken by teachers and researchers, indicating that there has been an increase in activities carried out by students and teachers with statements on student worksheets.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results, it can be concluded that the use of the talking stick method can improve the mastery of English vocabulary in class VII students of Mts Al-Khautshar, Kao. The talking stick media used to help mastering English vocabulary. The aspect of mastery of English vocabulary that is

emphasized in the use of the talking stick is the aspect of reading vocabulary and pronouncing vocabulary. The use of talking stick media can help students to read vocabulary individually in groups.

Some suggestions from the research results are: for the students are expected to be more diligent in writing vocabulary and paying attention. Students are expected to read more vocabulary so that students' vocabulary mastery can increase.

For teachers are expected to optimize the learning media in deliver material to increase student enthusiasm and create lessons are more varied.

References

- Astuti, C. A. (2017) Penerapan model pembelajaran kooperatif tipe talking stick berbantuan media gambar untuk meningkatkan hasil belajar. *Jurnal Wacana Akademik*, Vol. 1, No. 2, pp 109-1
- Basuki, B. E. (2017) Peningkatan hasil belajar IPA dengan metode talking stick siswa kelas V SDN 2 watuagung dongko treggalek. *Jurnal pembelajaran sains*, Vol. 1, No. 2, pp 34-35.
- Dewi, N. P. D. A., Wiyasa, I. K. N., & Asri , I. G. A. A. S. (2017) Pengaruh model kooperatif talking stick berbantuan question card terhadap kompetensi pengetahuan IPS siswa kelas IV. *Jurnal PGSD Universitas Pendidikan Ganesha*, Vol. 5, No. 2, pp 1-4.
- Firdaus, M. (2016) Penerapan model pembelajaran kooperatif tipe numbered heads together (NHT) di tinjau dari aktivitas belajar siswa kelas VII SMP. *Jurnal Formatif*, Vol. 6, No. 2, pp 93-94.
- Hayati, P. N., & Dewi , R. M. (2017) Pengaruh model pembelajaran talking stick terhadap hasil belajar siswa kelas X Sma Negeri 17 Surabaya. *Jurnal Pendidikan Ekonomi*, Vol. 5, No. 3, pp 1-3.
- Herlina, (2015) Meningkatkan pemhaman kosakata bahasa inggris melalui metode permainan bingo. *Jurnal ilmiah visi PPTK PAUDNI*, Vol. 10, No. 2, pp 114-115.
- Kusuma C. S. D. (2018) *Integrasi bahasa inggris dalam proses pembelajaran*. *Jurnal Efisiensi-Kajian Ilmu Administrasi*, Vol. xv, No. 2, pp 1-4.
- Lie, A. (2002) *Cooperative learning (Mempraktikan cooperative leraning di Ruang-ruang kelas*. PT Grasindo,
- Loi , O. P. , & Tamba , S. B. , & Pangaribun , M., & Saragih, E. (2020) Using flash expression book as instructional media to vocabulary mastery in learning English. *Jurnal Pendidikan Bahasa Inggris Undiksha*, Vol. 8, No. 2, pp 1-75.
- Nurmaulidiyah , M. ,& Dalle , A, & Fathimah , S. , *Penerapan model pembelajaran kooperatif tipe talking stick dalam keterampilan berbicara bahasa jerman siswa kelas XI Sma Negeri 2 Majene*.
- Santoso , I. (2014) Pembelajaran bahasa asing di Indonesia antara globalisasi dan hegemoni. *Jurnal Bahasa & Sastra*. Vol. 14, No. 1, pp 1-2.
- Setyowati , L. (2019) Meningkatkan kemampuan bahasa inggris measiswa universitas satya negara Indonesia melauai pembelajaran ILELTS dan TOELC dengan teknologi aplikasi android. *Jurnal pengabdian kepada masyarakat*, Vol.10, No.1, pp. 126-127.

Suhardian , I. P. A. (2018) Model pembelajaran talking stick sebagai pendukung penguasaan English vocabulary pada anak usia dini, *Vol. 3, No. 1, pp 41-43.*

Suyatno (2009) *menjelajahi pembelajaran inovatif*. Sidoarjo:Msmedia Buana Puataka.

Wibsono , S. , & Gusniarti , U. , & Nurtjahjo , F. E. (2017) *Pembelajaran kooperatif sebagai upaya meningkatkan motivasi, empati dan perilaku bekerja sama. Journal of psychological research, Vol. 3, No. 1, pp 1-4.*

Sulistiana, E., & Nadzifan , W .& Arifin, S. (2019) intensive english program (IEP) meningkatkan penguasaan vocabulary, *Jurnal studi guru dan pembelajaran , Vol. 2, No. 3, pp 236-237.*

Widyasari, F. E. (2016) Pembelajaran bahasa inggris dengan menggunakan metode multiple intelligences: studi kasus di sekolah internasional. *Jurnal Edutama, Vol. 3, No. 1, pp 31-31.*

Zalmansyah , A. (2013) Meningkatkan perbendaharaan kata (vocabulary) siswa dengan menggunakan komik strip sebagai media pembelajaran bahasa inggris. *Jurnal Kandai, Vol. 9, No. 2, pp 263-264.*

<https://suhadinet.wordpress.com/2009/06/08/langkah-langkah-ptk-menurut-kemmis-dan-mctaggart/>.

<https://docplayer.info/30470744-BaBii-kajian-teori-pengajaran-bahasa-asing-telah-berkembang-diindonesia-seiring-dengan.html>.

